

Formation Constants of Protonated Amidinothiourea*

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The reactions of amidinothiourea, $\text{NH}_2-(\text{S}=\text{C})-\text{NH}-\text{C}(\text{=NH})-\text{NH}_2$, with metal ions¹ and their analytical applications²⁻⁵ are reported in the literature, but the protonation of amidinothiourea has not yet been investigated. The protonation reaction may be represented as follows:

where B represents a molecule of amidinothiourea. The first (K_1) and the second (K_2) formation constants of protonated amidinothiourea are given by

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{BH}^+]}{[\text{B}][\text{H}^+]} \quad \text{and} \quad K_2 = \frac{[\text{BH}_2^{++}]}{[\text{BH}^+][\text{H}^+]}$$

at constant ionic strength.

In the present investigation the formation of protonated amidinothiourea has been followed by pH-measurements and the formation constants have been determined by Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁶.

All solutions were prepared in double distilled water. A known weight of pure amidinothiourea, prepared by the method of Kurzer⁷, was dissolved in a known volume of water to prepare the stock solution and its strength was determined by estimating amidinothiourea as its nickel complex, NiL_2 , where L represents a molecule of amidinothiourea less one hydrogen atom. Perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate solutions were standardised by known methods⁸. pH-measurements were taken with a Radiometer pH-meter using glass and calomel electrodes supplied by the Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute, Calcutta. The pH-meter was calibrated with aqueous phthalate buffer of pH 4.01 and checked with a borax buffer solution of pH 9.14. The titration was carried out in a 250 ml. Pyrex beaker covered with a wooden cover provided with five holes for inserting two electrodes, a burette, a stirrer and a thermometer. The beaker

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2. Nadkarni and Haldar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, 11, 427.
3. *Idem*, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 319.
4. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1964, 41, 813.
5. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1965, 42, 5.
6. Irving and Rossotti, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
7. Kurzer, *Organic Synthesis* (John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York), 1955, 35, 69.
8. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", (Longmans Green & Co., London), 1962.

was kept in a thermostat maintained at $32^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$. In one set, a mixture of 2.5 ml. of 4.0 M NaClO_4 + 30 ml. of 0.01 M amidinothiourea + 47.5 ml. water in a beaker and a mixture of 2.5 ml. of 4.0 M NaClO_4 + 97.5 ml. water in another beaker were titrated against 1.0 M HClO_4 . Similar titrations were performed with different concentrations of amidinothiourea and perchloric acid, keeping the ionic strength of the solution constant. The stability of amidinothiourea under the experimental conditions employed was tested by measuring the optical density near its absorption maximum (265 $m\mu$). A typical titration curve is shown in figure 1. The pK -values for the formation constants are tabulated in Table I.

FIG. 1. pH-meter reading as a function of the drops of HClO_4 (0.1 M) added to solution containing (a) 0.1 M NaClO_4 and (b) 0.1 M NaClO_4 + 0.001 M ATU. Total volume is 100 ml.

TABLE I

Formation constants of protonated amidinothiourea
 $T = 32^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$

Conc. ATU	Conc. HClO_4	Conc. NaClO_4	pK_1	pK_2
0.0005 M	0.05 M	0.1 M	5.20 ± 0.09	3.11 ± 0.07
0.001 M	0.1 M	0.1 M	5.25 ± 0.07	3.06 ± 0.09
0.005 M	0.1 M	0.1 M	5.30 ± 0.08	3.14 ± 0.10
0.01 M	0.5 M	0.1 M	5.25 ± 0.09	3.10 ± 0.08
0.05 M	2.275 M	0.1 M	5.21 ± 0.09	3.04 ± 0.04
0.001 M	0.1 M	0.05 M	5.22 ± 0.01	3.06 ± 0.10
0.001 M	0.1 M	0.01 M	5.22 ± 0.07	3.01 ± 0.15
0.001 M	0.1 M	0.005 M	5.22 ± 0.06	3.06 ± 0.10

